

IMPACT AGRICULTURE MARKETING ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF FARMERS WITH REFERENCE TO RYTHU BAZAARS IN ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The Government of Andhra Pradesh has established Rythu Bazaars in the year 1999 for the empowerment of farmers, who are selling their agricultural produce, especially the vegetables and fruits directly to the customers without interference of middlemen. This study aims to investigate the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the socio-economic status of these farmers. In this purpose the study selected East Godavari district in Andhra Pradesh state as study area and the selective six Rythu Bazaars in the six major cities in the district are study units. From each Rythu Bazaar 20 farmers were selected for the data collection. These farmers regularly bring the vegetables/fruits to these markers from their fields and sell directly to the consumers without interference of middlemen. Thus, the findings of this study revealed that a predominant group of farmers observed impact of Rythu Bazaars found more on their social status, household income and their nutritional food habits. Whereas a significant number of farmers expressed that they could increase their household savings and financial status with reducing their household debts. This leads to increase their land holdings and household assets. Thus it is found that the overall impact of Rythu Bazaars on socio-economic aspects of the farmers found positive significance on their socio-economic status.

Keywords: Agriculture Markets, Rythu Bazaars, Farmers, Socio-Economic Status

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INTRODUCTION

India's dependence on agricultural activities is huge. A large numbers of the population depends on agriculture. In India, two-thirds of the population depends on agriculture for their livelihood. It is the largest producer of agriculture products, and ranks as the second largest producer of rice, wheat, sugarcane, groundnut, vegetables, fruit and cotton (Arvind Shukla, 2021). With food being the crowning need of mankind, much emphasis has been on commercialising agricultural production. For this reason agriculture with its allied sectors, is the largest source of livelihoods in India. Therefore, 70 percent of its rural households still depend primarily on agriculture for their livelihood, with 82 percent of farmers being small and marginal (FAO, 2021). Since, agriculture stood as a substantial source of economic activity, it is providing livelihoods for extensive segments of the population. According to Jana and Basu (2024), approximately 53.0 percent of the working population in India engaged in agriculture. In contrast, though they are the backbone of the economy still they are facing many problems that not only affect them but also other people. Although farmers feed the entire nation sometimes they can't even afford two square meals for them and their families. So, many farmers left their farming work and went to some nearby industries (Goyal, et al., 2016). In this regard agricultural sector need efficient agricultural marketing, which plays an important role in the growth and development of farming and agricultural outputs essential for the rural development of India. Thus, agriculture production and agricultural marketing are two side of a coin for the rural development in general and improve the status of farmers in particular. When looking at agricultural production, it directly provides employment and life to rural India and on the other hand agricultural marketing helps in increasing the income of farmers and makes quality food availability in the country (Himanshu Arora, 2017), tends accelerates the development of rural India. Moreover, marketing of agricultural produce is considered as an integral part of agriculture, agriculture marketing is mainly the process of selling and buying of agriculture produce from farmer to consumer (Kiruthiga, et al., 2015). Thus, agricultural marketing is mainly the buying and selling of agricultural products and agricultural market plays a greater important role in development of rural economy through self-employment, income generation, food security and developing rural-market linkages.

AGRICULTURE MARKETING

Agricultural marketing covers the services involved in moving an agricultural product from the farm to the consumer. These services involve the planning, organizing, directing and handling of agricultural produce in such a way as to satisfy farmers, intermediaries and consumers (Prasaima, 2005). The majority of agricultural commodities in India are typically sold by farmers in the private sector to either moneylenders, who the farmers may owe money to, or village traders. Products are distributed through diverse channels. The farmers' markets provide consumers with the opportunity to obtain locally sourced and freshly harvested agricultural products and also facilitate farmers in establishing personal interaction with their customers and fostering loyalty among consumers towards the growers of the produce (Takle, et al., 2011). Therefore, agricultural marketing in India holds immense significance due to its strengthening aims to create favourable conditions under which farmers can effectively sell their produce directly to the consumers without middlemen interventions (Achrya and Agarwal, 2015). Thus, to overcome these problems the Andhra Pradesh Government established the concept of Ryrhu Bazara in the year 1999 to create a platform where farmers could sell their produce directly to the consumers without the interference of middlemen or marketing intermediaries (Subhendu Dey, 2012).

RYTHU BAZAARS

Rythu Bazaar is an initiative to uplift small and marginal farmers by directly connecting them to the consumer through the setting up of Rythu Bazaars in residential areas with permanent complexes (Gangadhara Rao, 2011). Rythu Bazaars are a fundamental part of the urban–rural interface, they have continued to grow in popularity, mostly due to the growing consumer interest in obtaining fresh products, especially produce directly from the farm. Rythu Bazaars allow consumers to have access to locally grown, farm-fresh produce, enable farmers to develop personal relationships with their customers, and cultivate consumer loyalty with the farmers who grow the produce (Purushothama Reddy, 2022). Direct marketing of farm products through Rythu Bazaars continues to be a significant sales outlet for agricultural producers nationwide. In these Rythu Bazaar consumers can buy fresh vegetables, fruits, and many other agricultural products directly from farmers. But unlike a normal transaction where one goes and buys a product from a seller, here, there is a chance of directly interacting with the farmers. This type of markets will help to interact with farmers and consumers and know more about sustainability, ecological and economic development (Rao, 2001). Therefore, these Rythu Bazaars not only help the farmers to fetch better prices for their produce but also consumers will inculcate the habit of getting fresh vegetables and agriculture products, which leads to clean eating with less to no wastage of food.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dewang Pagare et al. (2023) studied on small farmer's market choice in the presence of multiple markets in Indian, where they examined the decision-making process of small farmers when faced with multiple market options in India. Based on the study, it is found that a small farmer has the option to sell his/her products through three different markets, i.e. a government-regulated market, a corporate-owned market with high-quality standards and a fixed-price market operated by a government procurement centre. Thus, this study illustrates that corporate-owned and government-regulated markets are motivated to keep their markets separate by upholding distinct quality standards. This study highlights the significance of the minimum quality standards and prices available in markets when small farmers make decisions about which markets to participate in. These factors are found to be more influential than traditional considerations like transportation costs and minimum support prices. Pankaj Thakur et al. (2023) studied on marketing performance and factors influencing farmers' choice for agricultural output marketing channels. In this study the authors examined the relationship between marketing performance and the factors that influence farmers' decisions regarding agricultural output marketing channels. The study found that farmers who directly sold their peas to consumers achieved superior marketing performance compared to those who utilised market intermediaries such as local traders, commission agents, and wholesalers. Moreover, the findings revealed that factors such as farm income, farm experience, distance to the market, and market information played a significant role in influencing farmers' selection of marketing channels, the primary obstacles encountered by farmers were a deficiency in market consultancy, exorbitant commission charges and inadequate transportation. Dey and Singh (2023) studied on role of market participation on the wellbeing of smallholder vegetable farmers. This study aims to identify the factors that influence vegetable farmers' participation in the market and assess the effects of this participation on households' well-being. The findings from the propensity score matching approach (PSM) and endogenous switch regression (ESR) methods indicate that engaging in the vegetable market has a positive and significant effect on the income and consumption expenditure of small-scale farmers.

Additionally, the research shows that the size of the household, proximity to the market, income from non-farming sources, availability of training, knowledge of prices, ownership of a vehicle, and the presence of storage facilities are all important factors that influence vegetable farmers' involvement in the market. Rengasamy, et al. (2023) studied on farmers' markets in Tamil Nadu with reference to increasing options for rural producers and improving access for urban consumers. This study described that with the increasing popularity of farmers' markets in other Indian states and in many other parts of the world, important lessons can be learnt from this experience, especially with regard to some important unintended or unanticipated benefits and costs, to the mechanisms for setting up such markets and to some additional measures which could have broadened and deepened the benefits for the poorest groups. Solanki and Inumula (2021) studied on the determinants of consumer attitudes and behavior with reference to farmers markets using an intercept survey design. This study investigated indicators of the attitudes, preferences, and characteristics of customers who shop at Indian farmers' markets. It is found that while approximately 80% of consumers in Cluster 1 were willing to pay more at the farmers' market than at a nearby retail outlet or supermarket, in Cluster 2 consisted of consumers who prefer value for money, but Cluster 3 consisted of consumers who rated the market's hygiene and service conditions highly. This study concludes that consumers are satisfied with the operation of farmers' markets near their homes. Varghese Subi (2021) studied on impact of Alwal Rythu Bazaar on farmers examine the problems of farmers/sellers and their overall satisfaction levels towards these markets. It is observed that the farmers who bring their produce directly from their fields are facing problems in transportation, selling of produce, stall occupancy, etc. Smithers John (2019) studied on farmers' markets and observed that there is a growing social appetite for the available food products and the modern food system. The reasons for this are rehearsed elsewhere in this volume in relation to local food and in an expansive and expanding literature on alternative agri-food networks. It is found that while there is much variation in the scale, structure, and organizational details among and between specific iterations of this form of food marketing, a farmers' market is generally understood to be a regularly recurring market at a fixed geographical location with or without association. Kumar and Mukherjee (2018) studied on marketing behavior of vegetable growers in Uttarakhand hills. This study provides a distinctive insight into the complexities of agricultural trade in hilly areas. By examining the tactics and obstacles encountered by vegetable growers, the research reveals the adaptive measures essential for effective marketing. The findings hold substantial importance for the agricultural sector, offering valuable perspectives for sustainable development in hill regions and showcasing the resilience of local farmers in overcoming geographical challenges.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this paper is to study the impact agriculture marketing on socio-economic aspects of farmers with reference to Rythu Bazaars in Andhra Pradesh for which the perceptions of the farmers about various socio-economic aspects of farmers influenced by Rythu Bazaars. This study seeks to explore the socio-economic structure of farmers participating in these markets, shedding light on their demographic profile, landholding patterns, income levels, and other relevant factors. In this purpose this study endeavours to gauge the perceptions of farmers towards the efficiency of these markets, elucidating their attitudes, preferences, challenges faced, and expectations for improvement. Hence, the following objectives outlined to study in this research.

1. To study the socio economic structure of farmers marketing the vegetables at Rythu Bazaars.
2. To study the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the status of farmers with reference to their socio-economic variables.

Hypothesis

H₁: There is no significance difference in the perceptions of various demographic group farmers towards impact of Rythu Bazaars on status of farmers

H₂: The impact of Rythu Bazaars on status of farmers does not influenced by their socio-economic aspects

METHODOLOGY

The study is grounded in a comprehensive data collection approach, encompassing both primary and secondary data sources. For the primary data Rythu Bazaars located in Erstwhile East Godavari district in Andhra Pradesh were chosen for its significant relevance in vegetable and fruit marketing by the farmers. Thus, the data collection process employed by the researcher in a multi-stage random sampling technique, where in the selected district six Rythu Bazaars have been chosen and from each one 20 farmers have be selected. The selective six Rythu Bazaars in study district are strategically located in various urban and semi-urban areas to ensure accessibility for farmers to sell their agriculture produce in these markers. These Rythu Bazaars are: Kakinada, Rajahmundry, Amalapuram, Peddapuram, Ramachandrapuram and Samalkota.

DATA ANALYSIS

After data collection it was processed through SPSS and designed the output results in table format and analysed. Thus, the data was analysed by frequencies, percentages, mean and rank analysis by scores and ANOVA test to find out the differences of various socio-demographic group farmers towards impact of Rythu Bazaars. In addition to these statistics regression analysis has been done to examine the influence of socio-economic variables of farmers on the impact of Rythu Bazaars with reference to status of farmers. In this model of regression the researcher estimated the level of impact of Rythu Bazaars with reference to status of farmers who carry their agriculture produce, especially fruits and vegetables, to these market yards and sell to consumers directly without the intervention of middlemen. Hence, the level of impact of Rythu Bazaars with reference to status of farmers has estimated with the change in Household income, Household savings, Social status, Nutrition food habits, Household debts, Household assets, Land holdings and Financial status with the help of Likert's three-point scale method, where increased response valued with 2, no change response valued with 1 and decreased response valued with 0. The total score of all these aspects considered as impact of Rythu Bazaars on the status of farmers, and the socio-economic variables of farmers considered as independent variables.

PERSONAL INFORMATION

This information deals with the demographic details of the farmers of Rythu Bazaars like gender, age, caste, religion, education, income, etc., and household details like type of family, dwelling house and land holdings. Thus, the details of each one are presented in the following tables.

Table-1: Distribution of farmers in the selective Rythu Bazaars with reference to their Socio-Economic variables

Demographic variables	Demographic groups	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	54	45.0
	Female	66	55.0
Age	Below 20 years	11	9.2
	21-30 years	26	21.7
	31-40 years	29	24.2
	41-50 years	25	20.8
	51-60 years	23	19.2
	Above 61 years	6	5.0
Caste	OC	18	15.0
	BC	61	50.8
	SC	14	11.7
	ST	16	13.3
	Others	11	9.2
Literacy level	Illiterate	45	37.5
	Primary	44	36.7
	Secondary	12	10.0
	Under Graduation	10	8.3
	Graduation &above	9	7.5
Primary Occupation	Cultivation	58	48.3
	Landless labour	42	35.0
	Vegetable vendor	20	16.7
Average income per day	Below 500	17	14.2
	501 to 1000	44	36.7
	1001 to1500	28	23.3
	1501 to2000	16	13.3
	Above 2000	15	12.5
Living status	Hut	16	13.3
	Asbestos	49	40.8
	Tilled	33	27.5
	Concrete roof	22	18.3
Average land holdings	Below 0.5	19	15.8
	0.5-1.0	51	42.5
	1.0-2.0	32	26.7
	Above 2.0	18	15.0
Land using pattern for vegetables and fruits	Less than 1 acre	49	40.8
	1-3 acres	58	48.3
	More than 3 acres	13	10.8
Experience in vegetable vending	Less than 3 years	33	27.5
	3-6 years	60	50.0
	More than 6 years	27	22.5

Source: Survey Data

The Table-1 shows the distribution of farmers in selective Rythu Bazaars of East Godavari district with reference to their socio-economic variables. According to their gender-wise distribution it is noticed that 55.0 percent are female and 45.0 percent are male.

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Whereas the age-wise distribution of farmers revealed that 24.2 percent are in the age group of 31-40 years, followed by 21.7 percent are in the age group of 21-30 years, 20.8 percent are in the age group of 41-50 years, 19.2 percent are in the age group of 51-60 years, 9.2 percent are in the age group of below 20 years and 5.0 percent are in the age group of above 61 years. With reference to the caste-wise distribution of farmers in the selective Rythu Bazaars, it is found that dominated group of 50.8 percent belongs to BC caste, followed by 15.0 percent are OC caste, 13.3 percent belongs to ST caste, 11.7 percent belongs to SC caste and 9.2 percent belongs to other castes. While the literacy levels of farmers shows 37.5 percent are illiterates, 36.7 percent are with primary level education, 10.0 percent are with secondary level education, 8.3 percent are under graduates and 7.5 percent are studied graduation & above. But the primary occupational status of farmers revealed that as many as 48.3 percent are in cultivation, and from the rest 35.0 percent are landless labourers and 16.7 percent are vegetable vendors. Regarding the average per-day income levels of the farmers shows that 36.7 percent are earning between Rs.501-1000, 23.3 percent are earning between Rs.1001-1500 and 13.3 percent are earning between Rs.1501-2000, but 14.2 percent are earning below Rs.500 and 12.5 percent are earning above Rs.2000.

The living status of the farmers in selective Rythu Bazaars, the data shows that a predominant group of 40.8 percent are living in asbestos houses, and from the rest 27.5 percent are living in tiled houses, 18.3 percent are living in concrete roof houses and 13.3 percent are living in huts. Whereas, the land holding status of farmers observed that as many as 42.5 percent have 0.5-1.0 acres of land, 26.7 percent have 1.0-2.0 acres of land, 15.8 percent have below 0.5 acres of land and 15.0 percent have above 2.0 acres of land. Since, the average size of land utilised for vegetable farming shows that a dominated group of 48.3 percent of farmers are using 1-3 acres of land for vegetable farming, 40.8 percent of farmers are using less than 1 acre of land and only 10.8 percent of farmers are using more than acres of land for vegetable farming. But vegetable vending experience of the farmers in the Rythu Bazaars indicate that majority group of 50.0 percent are engaged in vegetable vending for 3-6 years, and from the remaining 27.5 percent are engaged in vegetable vending for less than 3 years and 22.5 percent are engaged in this profession for more than 6 years.

Table-2: Impact of Rythu Bazaar on socio-economic status of farmers

S. No	Statements	Decreased	No change	Increased	Total
1	Household income	24 (20.0)	38 (31.7)	58 (48.3)	120 (100.0)
2	Household savings	30 (25.0)	41 (34.2)	49 (40.8)	120 (100.0)
3	Social status	21 (17.5)	52 (43.3)	47 (39.2)	120 (100.0)
4	Nutrition food habits	26 (21.7)	45 (37.5)	49 (40.8)	120 (100.0)
5	Household debts	38 (31.7)	48 (40.0)	34 (28.3)	120 (100.0)
6	Household assets	41 (34.2)	54 (45.0)	25 (20.8)	120 (100.0)
7	Land holdings	39 (32.5)	51 (42.5)	30 (25.0)	120 (100.0)
8	Financial status	33 (27.5)	47 (39.2)	40 (33.3)	120 (100.0)

Source: Survey Data

Perceptions of farmers about the impact of Rythu Bazaar on their socio-economic aspects are presented in the Table-2. While 48.3 percent of the farmers said that their household income is increased with the Rythu Bazaars, 31.7 percent said there is no change in their household income and 20.0 percent said their household income is decreased. Whereas, 40.8 percent opined their household savings are increased and 34.2 percent opined there is no change, but 25.0 percent opined their household savings are decreased. Since, 43.3 percent of the farmers said there is no change their social status, 39.2 percent said that their social status is increased and 17.5 percent said their social status is decreased. It is found that a dominated group of 40.8 percent farmers said their nutritional food habits are increased, from the rest, 37.5 percent said there is no change in nutrition food habits but 21.7 percent said their nutrition food habits are decreased.

According to the data 40.0 percent said there is no change in household debts, but 31.7 percent said household debts are decreased and 28.3 percent only said their household debts are increased. While a majority group of 45.0 percent farmers said that there is no change in their household assets with the influence of Rythu Bazaars, 34.2 percent said household assets are decreased and 20.8 percent only said that their household assets are increased. It is observed that 42.5 percent farmers expressed no change in their land holdings, but 32.5 percent said their land holdings have decreased and 25.0 percent said their land holdings have increased with the impact of Rythu Bazaars. Hence, it is found that 39.2 percent farmers said that there is no change in their financial status with the affect of Rythu Bazaars, whereas 33.3 percent said their financial status is increased and 27.5 percent said financial status has decreased.

Table-3: Rank order analysis of socio-economical impact of Rythu Bazaar on the farmers

S. No	Statements	Decreased	No change	Increased	Total
	Scale Value (SV)	1	2	3	
1	Household income	24	38	58	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	24	76	174	274-I
2	Household savings	30	41	49	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	30	82	147	259-IV
3	Social status	21	52	47	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	21	104	141	266-II
4	Nutrition food habits	26	45	49	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	26	90	147	263-III
5	Household debts	38	48	34	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	38	96	102	236-VI
6	Household assets	41	54	25	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	41	108	75	224-VIII
7	Land holdings	39	51	30	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	39	102	90	231-VII
8	Financial status	33	47	40	120
	Frequency x Scale Value	33	94	120	247-V
	Total Score				2000
	Maximum Possible Score	3(Maximum score points) 120 (number of respondents) x 8 (number of statements)			2880
	Percentage of score	Total score of impact of Rythu Bazaars/Maximum score x 100			69.4
	Average	Total score / Number of statements			250.0

Source: Survey Data

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The Table-3 represents the rank order analysis of socio-economical impact of Rythu Bazaar on the farmers. There are 8 socio-economical impact aspects are presented in the table with reference to Rythu Bazaars, and each one is carrying an individual score on the basis of respondents' perceptions. Based on the scores the ranks have been given to each statement and the rank order analysis has been discussed in the following. According to the above table data, it can be understood that the 1st rank is given to the aspect "Household income" with a score value of 274, 2nd rank has been given to the aspect "Social status" with a score value of 266. In this process the 3rd rank is given to the aspect "Nutrition food habits" with a score value of 263, and the 4th rank is given to the aspect "Household savings" which is carrying a score value of 259. While the 5th rank is given to the aspect "Financial status" with a score value of 247, the 6th rank is given to the aspect "Household debts" with a score value of 236. The 7th rank is given to the aspect "Land holdings" with a score value of 231 and 8th rank is given to the aspect "Household assets" which is secured a score value of 224. With reference to the scores of the 8 statements the total score obtained was 2000 and the average score is 250.0.

Thus, the perceptions of farmers about the impact of Rythu Bazaars on their socio-economical status revealed that as many as 82.5 percent felt impact of Rythu Bazaars found more on their social status, so 80.0 percent observed felt impact on their household income. While 78.3 percent farmers opined impact of Rythu Bazaars influenced on their nutrition food habits, 75.0 percent of the farmers felt that the Rythu Bazaars impact on increasing their household savings. Thus, 72.5 percent of the farmers opined that there is a increase of financial status found with the help of Rythu Bazaars. Moreover, 68.3 percent farmers felt that Rythu Bazaars helped to reduce their their household debts, above sixty percent opined their land holdings (67.5%) were increased. This leads to increase the household assets of 65.8 percent farmers. Thus it is found that the overall impact of Rythu Bazaars on socio-economic aspects of the farmers found positive and increase their status.

Moreover, the Government of Andhra Pradesh has established Rythu Bazaars for empowerment of farmers, who are selling their agricultural produce, especially the vegetables and fruits, directly to the customers without interference of middlemen, this study aims to investigate the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the socio-economic status of these farmers. In this purpose the perceptual score on the socio-economic status of farmers has been established and showed in the above table. Since, the farmers who are selling their goods in the Rythu Bazaars are from various demographic groups, the difference in the socio-economic status they achieved with the Rythu Bazaars are distinguished in the following Table-4 and analysed.

Table-4: Difference in the impact of socio-economic status among various demographic group farmers in Rythu Bazaars

Particulars	Category	N	Mean	Std dev	Std Err	f- value	p-value
Gender	Male	54	16.76	2.180	0.297	0.177	0.675
	Female	66	16.59	2.184	0.269		
Age	Below 20 years	11	17.36	2.838	0.856	0.552	0.736
	21-30 years	26	16.69	2.363	0.463		
	31-40 years	29	16.48	2.309	0.429		
	41-50 years	25	16.48	2.182	0.436		
	51-60 years	23	16.96	1.581	0.330		
Caste	Above 61 years	6	15.83	1.472	0.601	0.938	0.445
	Other Community	18	15.89	1.997	0.471		
	Backward Community	61	16.95	2.077	0.266		
	Scheduled Caste	14	16.86	2.476	0.662		
	Scheduled Tribe	16	16.50	2.221	0.555		
Literacy level	Minorities	11	16.36	2.541	0.766	0.763	0.551
	Illiterate	45	16.67	2.276	0.339		
	Primary	44	16.57	2.172	0.327		
	Secondary	12	16.17	1.992	0.575		
Primary Occupation	Under Graduation	10	16.70	2.003	0.633	0.979	0.379
	Graduation & above	9	17.78	2.167	0.722		
	Cultivation	58	16.91	2.097	0.275		
	Land less labour	42	16.57	2.349	0.363		
	Vegetable vendor	20	16.15	2.007	0.449		
Income per day (in Rs.)	Below 500	17	16.47	1.875	0.455	1.315	0.269
	501 to 1000	44	16.64	1.989	0.300		
	1001 to 1500	28	17.29	2.417	0.457		
	1501 to 2000	16	16.75	2.436	0.609		
	Above 2000	15	15.73	2.154	0.556		
Total		120	16.67	2.174	0.199		

Source: Survey Data

With reference to gender groups of the farmers it is found that the average perceived score of male (16.76) found higher than their counterpart female (16.59), where the standard deviation of male is 2.180 and female is 2.184. But the calculated f-value 0.177 does not indicate any significance result because the p-value 0.675 is higher than 0.05. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the impact of Rythu Bazaar towards socio-economic status of male and female farmers. Among various age group farmers the average perceived score of below 20 years age group (17.36) found highest than the other groups and the lowest average score perceived by above 61 years age group (15.83), and the standard deviations are 2.838, and 1.472 respectively. With these mean and standard deviation differences among various age groups the calculated f-value 0.552 does not indicate any significance result because the p-value 0.736 is higher than 0.05. This infers that there is no significant difference in the impact of Rythu Bazaar towards socio-economic status of various age-group farmers.

Regarding to various caste group farmers it is observed that the average perceived score of Backward Community group (16.95) found higher than the other groups and the average perceived score of Other Community group (15.89) found lowest. And the respective standard deviations are 2.077 and 1.997. With the mean and standard deviation differences among various caste groups the calculated f-value 0.938 does not indicate any significance result because the p-value 0.445 is higher than 0.05. This infers that there is no significant difference in the impact of Rythu Bazaar towards socio-economic status of various caste group farmers.

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The perceptive score of various literacy level farmers towards their socio-economic status revealed that the average score of graduation and above qualified group (17.78) was found highest and the average score of secondary education group (16.17) was found least and the standard deviation of these two groups are 2.167 and 1.992 respectively. According to the mean and standard deviation differences among various literacy level groups the calculated f-value 0.763 indicates no significance because the p-value 0.551 is higher than 0.05. This concludes that there is no significant difference in the impact of Rythu Bazaar towards socio-economic status of various literacy level farmers.

With reference to various occupational group farmers the average perceptual scores towards impact of Rythu Bazaars on their socio-economic status, it shows that the average score of cultivation (16.91) found higher than other groups and vegetable score of vendors group (16.15) found lowest, and their respective standard deviations are 2.097 and 2.007. While the calculated f-value 0.979 does not indicate any significance result due to the p-value (0.379) shows higher than 0.05. This infers that there is no significant difference among various occupational group farmers towards the impact of Rythu Bazaar on their socio-economic status. Whereas, the average perceived scores of various per-day income level group farmers, it is found that the average score of Rs.1001 to Rs.1500 income group found the highest (17.29) than the other income groups and the average score of above Rs.2000 income group (15.73) was the lowest and their respective standard deviations of these groups are 2.417 and 2.154. In this regard the calculated f-value 1.315 indicate no significance result because the p-value 0.269 is higher than 0.05. This shows that there is no significant difference in the impact of Rythu Bazaars towards socio-economic status among various per-day income level group farmers.

Impact of Rythu Bazaars on socio-economic status of Farmers

The main objective of this paper is to study the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the socio-economic status of farmers. Thus, to estimate the impact of socio-economic aspects on socio-economic status of farmers with reference to Rythu Bazaars the regression more has been adopted in this study. Thus, the details of dependent and independent variables in this regression model are listed below:

Multiple Regression Model $Y = a + x_1b_1 + x_2b_2 + x_3b_3 + x_4b_4 + x_5b_5 + \dots$

Dependent Variable: Y = Impact of Rythu Bazaars on socio-economic status of farmers

Independent Variables:

x_1 → Gender – Dummy variable (1-Male, 0-Female)

x_2 → Age – Quantitative Variable, actual age of the respondents has considered

x_3 → Community / Caste – Dummy Variable (where OC and BC rated with 1 and others like SC and ST rated with 0)

x_4 → Level of Educational– Rank variable, where illiterates ranked with 0, primary ranked with 1, secondary ranked with 2, intermediate ranked with 3 and graduation and above ranked with 4

x_5 → Income per day – Quantitative variable measured by actual income levels of the respondent per day

x_6 → Land Holdings – Index Variable, where 1 for below 0.5 acres, 2 to 0.5-1.0 acres, 3 for 1.0-2.0 acres and 4 for above 2.0 acres

x_7 → Land used for vegetable farming – Index variable, where 1 for below 1.0 acres, 2 for 1-3 acres, 3 for above 3.0 acres

x₈ → Experience in vegetable vending – Quantitative variable, where actual number of years experience possessed by the farmers in vegetable vending

Table-4.46: Impact of Rythu Bazaars on status of Farmers with reference to their Socio-Economic variables

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable: Impact of Rythu Bazaars

R= 0.8295 R²= 0.6881 Adjusted R²= 0.6763

F(8,112)=58.201 p<0.0000 Std. Error of estimate: 0.2434

Independent variables	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t(112)	p-level
Intercept			0.83	0.10	8.60	0.00
Gender	0.43	0.17	0.33	0.13	2.54*	0.01
Age	0.03	0.18	0.03	0.13	0.19	0.85
Caste	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.08	0.92	0.36
Education qualification	0.25	0.09	0.20	0.08	2.66*	0.01
Income per day	0.16	0.06	0.14	0.05	2.63*	0.01
Land holdings	0.55	0.18	0.37	0.12	3.08**	0.00
Land used for vegetable farming	0.51	0.11	0.33	0.07	4.50**	0.00
Experience in vegetable vending	0.16	0.16	0.11	0.10	1.03	0.30

Source: Survey Data; * Significant at 5% level; ** Significant at 1% level

In this model of linear multiple regressions it is found best fit to measure the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the socio-economic status of farmers with referenced to their socio-economic aspects. This is because the F-value in this regression is 58.201 which found satisfactorily significant at 1% level because the p-value is less than 0.00. This model also explains R² at 67.63% of variation. In this model of regression analysis out of the total 8 explanatory variables of farmers’ socio-economic aspects as many as 5 variables are found to be significant, but three variables i.e. age, caste and experience in vegetable vending are not indicate any significance. Thus, the significant variables are gender, education qualification, per day income, land holdings and land used for vegetable forming. Among these significant variables land holdings and land used for vegetable forming are showing 1% significance and gender, education qualification and income per day variables are indicating 5% significance. This infers that these independent variables of socio-economic aspects of farmers are determining the impact of Rythu Bazaars towards socio-economic status of farmers. Here it is observed that male farmers found higher impact of Rythu Bazaars than their counterpart female farmers. Like that the farmers who are qualified more in their education found high level of impact by Rythu Bazaars. While the farmers, whose per day income levels shows more, the impact of Rythu Bazaars on their socio-economic status is high. It is important to note that the farmers who possess more and more land holdings and used their lands for vegetable farming are experiencing the higher impact of Rythu Bazaars on their socio-economic status.

CONCLUSION

The Government of Andhra Pradesh has established Rythu Bazaars in the year 1999 for the empowerment of farmers, who are selling their agricultural produce, especially the vegetables and fruits directly to the customers without interference of middlemen. This study aims to investigate the impact of Rythu Bazaars on the socio-economic status of these farmers. In this purpose the study selected East Godavari district in Andhra Pradesh state as study area and the selective six Rythu Bazaars in the six major cities in the district are study units. From each Rythu Bazaar 20 farmers were selected for the data collection. These farmers regularly bring the vegetables/fruits to these markers from their fields and sell directly to the consumers without interference of middlemen.

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Thus, the findings of this study revealed that a predominant group of farmers observed impact of Rythu Bazaars found more on their social status, household income and their nutritional food habits. Whereas a significant number of farmers expressed that they could increase their household savings and financial status with reducing their household debts. This leads to increase their land holdings and household assets. Thus it is found that the overall impact of Rythu Bazaars on socio-economic aspects of the farmers found positive significance on their socio-economic status.

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